

Language and Technology

Hoshimova Nazokatxon Shuhratjon qizi

O'zbekiston davlat Jahon tillari Filologiya fakulteti 3-kurs talabasi

- The impact of technology on language use and change
 - New forms of language use in digital spaces
 - Language and social media
 - Language and artificial intelligence

Scientific leader: **Sapayeva Sahiba**

Annotation: In this article the importance of 21st century innovative technologies in language learning, how learners can be interested in studying a new language through modern technologies, the use of effective methods during lessons will be discussed.

Key words: innovative, methodology, lexicon, phonetics, artificial intelligence, virtual screen, an exercise in dynamics, an exercise in statics, multimedia.

The role of language in the development of the nation, state, and society is very important, necessary and urgent. As the nation, state, and society progress, his love and attention to the language increases. Progress in social life determines progress in language.

The introduction of computer technologies into the educational process, especially language teaching, became a huge problem in the 20th century, because by the 21st century, in the information age, computer technology has been widely used in language teaching for the following purposes:

- a) use of computer programs in the process of teaching Uzbek as a mother tongue, Uzbek as a foreign language, and foreign languages. Certain works are being carried out in our country to solve this problem;
- b) use of computer data in teaching the grammar, phonetics and lexicon of the language;
- c) using a computer program to assess the knowledge of the Uzbek language and foreign languages.

All conditions and opportunities have been created for the comprehensive education of the growing young generation, their thorough acquisition of modern knowledge and skills. During these reforms, special attention was paid to the teaching of foreign languages. The decision "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 served as an important factor in this regard.

In the article "Artificial intelligence and language learning", B. Skinner shows the importance of the role of the computer in easy language learning. Working with a computer is convenient for working on oneself. When learning a language with the help of modern technologies, students learn to react to information and can analyze the weak, i.e., unclear areas of information. Technology is not only unique to

modern education, but it is the middle resource that implements the modern and innovative education of the future.

One of the modern technologies is the international blackboard. This board connects the two concepts of memory and proof. Blackboard consists of a virtual screen and layouts that enable teaching and learning. The Internet is a valuable resource for foreign language teachers. It contains a large amount of all types of certified documents.

The most common method of modern approaches today is mainly the use of multimedia in the lesson. Multimedia works of foreign language teachers have to stay for a long time in the real virtual space, facilitate the learning process of communication, and if the multimedia resource is interesting, it is easier to learn it.

The usefulness of multimedia tools is that when learning a language, you can see live games, that is, see pictures, hear sounds, and observe the activity of live games. In multimedia approaches, it is easy to assess mostly one person, because in multimedia approaches, learning through games is allowed. Therefore, the teacher has a pedagogical approach to each student. He tries to reveal the topic through various activities.

It is no exaggeration or mistake to say that learning a foreign language is a process of doing exercises. This is the dynamic side of the exercise. Its static (status) aspect is that it is organized in the form of educational material in the textbook. Exercise in statics means a teaching-methodical category, which is marked with a certain number or letter in a foreign language textbook or is specially highlighted, consists of two parts, and makes up the content of the lesson. The parts of the exercise are called "exercise requirement (title)" and "exercise material" in methodical literature.

A dynamic exercise is a learning activity performed by a student in a foreign language, from writing a letter or pronouncing a sound to comprehending a text or freely expressing one's thoughts.

The use of computer technologies in language teaching helps students to actively participate in the lesson. Technologies like these enable teachers to deliver presentations in a variety of ways to increase student interest. In addition, students can be interested in language learning by giving various tests or puzzles after the lesson.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methods were expressed. One of these views belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. In his opinion, although the teaching methodology of any subject is a science, it is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical issues. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching is not based only on the evidence of psychology, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great English linguist, O. Yespersen, who is considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. Bryuns and Brealya, prominent Anglicist and well-known phonetician V. Fyotor and others. Academician L.V.

Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist scientist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor V.A. Artemov gave a valuable opinion about the interrelationship of methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how a teacher conducts a lesson. Psychology deals with how students master this subject. However, one cannot fully agree with this opinion.

Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology. This article concludes that we are living in the era of advanced information technology, and it is necessary to teach foreign languages in a way that is understandable for everyone, using these facilities wisely. Therefore, introducing technologies and ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the time are the main tasks of pedagogues-scientists that cannot be delayed. Training of specialists and improvement of their qualifications is also relevant. While the economic, political, cultural and educational relations of our country with the countries of the world are growing, the interest of our youth in the life, culture, customs, and language of foreign countries is increasing. The role of foreign languages in the development of these relations is incomparable.

REFERENCES

1. Odiljonovna, T. M. (2023). THE PLACE AND IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. Innovation:

The journal of Social Sciences and Researches, 1(5), 112-113.

2. J. Jalolov "Methodology of foreign language teaching"

3. Decision No. 1875 of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" dated December 10, 2012